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Research Trend in Special Education in India: Retrospect and Prospect

Mr. Hemendra S. Mistry*

INTRODUCTION

All the children are different in relation to their mental and physical attributes. Some learn very fast but some need reasonable teaching-learning inputs for learning prescribed task. Some, as some children require additional support for meeting their special learning needs arising out of sensory, intellectual and physiological deficits. These special learning needs have given rise to the component of education known as special education which employs special instructional methodology, teaching-learning aids and equipment and managerial competencies to meet educational needs of the persons in the specific disability.

Research in Special Education, as a subject of independent existence in literature on educational research, is a recent development. The first review of research in special education in the Encyclopaedia of Educational Research (Mitzel, 1982) appeared in 1982 and in the first Handbook of Special Education (Kauffman *et al.*, 1982) in 1983. The first Encyclopaedia of Special Education (Reynolds *et al.*, 1987) is as recent as 1987. In our own country, this area has received attention from the Fourth Survey of Research in Education. The first three surveys (Buch, 1974, 1979, 1986) did not identify sufficient researches to warrant independent review of trends. (Jangira and Mukhopadhyay, 1991). However, an attempt was made at the NCERT by Jangira and Mukhopadhyay (1991) to catalogue and review research in special education in India. The present paper is based on the special education studies abstracted in fourth to sixth surveys of research in education and areas covered in those researches. Further, the paper focuses mainly on four major categories of disability viz. Visual Impairment (VI), Hearing Impairment (HI), Orthopaedically Handicap (OH) and Mental Retardation (MR). Research at PG level is excluded as they are limited in terms of coverage of sample and variable. Table-1 presents yearwise and disabilitywise distribution of doctoral and institutional researches carried out till the sixth survey of research in education in India.

Table 1: Yearwise and Categorywise Distribution of Researches in Special Education

Survey	Year	VI	HI	OH	MR	LD	Gifted	Misc	Other	Total
Fourth	1983-1987	01	--	05	06	01	04	04	02	23
Fifth	1988-1992	05	06	04	05	07	--	08	06	41
Sixth	1993-2005	06	03	04	07	06	--	06	13	45
Grand Total		12	09	13	18	14	04	18	21	109

(VI: Visually Impaired HI: Hearing Impaired OH: Orthopaedic Impaired MR: Mental Retardation LD: Learning Disability)
(Source: 4th (1991) and 5th (1997) Survey of Research in Education, http://eduresearch.dauniv.ac.in/search_result.asp)

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In all, 109 studies have been recorded from the fourth to sixth survey period. The number of studies has been increased. Studies on all the major category of disability have been reported during the fifth and sixth survey period. The largest number of studies in a single year (12) appeared in 1991. Studies were conducted in different departments as special education is now being a multidisciplinary area. Table-2 summarizes yearwise and discipline specific studies.

Table 2: Yearwise and Discipline Specific Distribution of Researches in Special Education

Survey	Year	Education	Psychology	Home Sci.	Eco.	Lang.	Phy. Edu.	Institutional	Total
Fourth	1983-1987	10	04	--	01	--	--	08	23
Fifth	1988-1992	13	04	01	--	01	--	17 + 05*	41
Sixth	1993-2005	38	04	02	--	--	01	--	45
Grand Total		61	12	03	01	01	01	25 + 05*	109

(*Indian Educational Review) (Source: 4th (1991) and 5th (1997) Survey of Research in Education, http://eduresearch.dauuniv.ac.in/search_result.asp)

It can be seen that in all, sixty-one studies were reported in education, twelve in psychology, three one each in economics, languages and physical education and two in home-science. Out of the 109, twenty-five studies have been reported as institutional/independent studies financed by NCERT, ICSSR, UGC, ERIC and UNICEF agencies and organizations while five studies have been reported under Indian Educational Review.

AREAWISE REVIEW AND DISCUSSION OF STUDIES

Education of Visually Impaired

Twelve studies on education of visually impaired persons were reported till the period of sixth survey of research in education. Two studies investigated the adjustment of blind children (Pandey, 1985 and Banerjee, 1988). Sahoo (1991) carried out study on characteristics of deaf-dumb and normal students and food habits (Bharti, 2001). Muruganandam (1990) developed an intelligence test and science teaching-learning strategy while Mulwan (1999) constructed verbal group test of intelligence. Only one study (Sharma, 1988) conducted on mainstreaming of visually impaired and issues and challenges in integrated education (Sudarsan, 1999). Three studies (Khan, 1988; Lal, 1992 and Vyas, 1995) were conducted on personality of visually impaired students.

Education of Children with Neuromuscular and Orthopaedic Impairment

Thirteen studies have been reported in this area. Bala (1985); Goel (1986); Sharma (1990) compared variables across disability. The studies of Upreti (1988), Chudasama (1992) and Kamthan (2002) compared orthopaedically handicapped children with non-disabled children on selected variables, like need achievement and reaction to frustration; self-concept, need pattern and intelligence; adjustment, aggressiveness, achievement-motivation; personality dimensions respectively. Bala (1985) compared them on measures of personality. Pathaks (1984) is the only study covering the learning environment in an integrated setting while self-concept and adjustment and segregated environment was studied by Pradhan (1993). Social and psychological factors of family (Tangri, 1990) and adjustment, self-concept, alienation and altruism of siblings of OH (Satsangi, 1993) were also reported.

The number of
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multidisciplinary

Education of the Hearing Impaired

Only nine studies could be located in this area. Three studies covered hearing impaired as a subsample (Bala, 1985; Goel, 1986 and Kapoor, 1990). These are the studies comparing hearing-impaired children with non-hearing-impaired children on selected variables. Paranjpe (1991) and Maudke (1991) measured effectiveness of supplementary education programme, single modality stimulation upon language development while Sharma and Pandey (1992) and Reddy (1993) measured

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respectively. Janigra and Ahuja (1990) and Pandey (1991) studied disabled and disabled in newspaper and in rural society respectively.

TREND OF SPECIAL EDUCATION RESEARCH IN INDIA

The trend of special education research in India has been :

- Out of the total 109 reported studies, 74.47 percent of the total studies were conducted at Ph. D. level and remained 25.53 percent were at institutional or independent level. The most explored areas are other categories of disability and misc researchers which falls about 35 percent of the total studies while the least researched area is hearing disability as only 09 studies have been reported.

- Different researchers followed different research procedures according to the nature of the problem selected by them but majority of the research studies were followed survey type around fifty-five percent. However, the trend increased towards experimental studies during the sixth survey period as 18 experimental studies have been reported during the sixth survey period. Qualitative methods do not seem to find a place with researchers.

- In most of the researches, samples were of single disability from integrated or special schools but the level of disability have not been specified properly. Some studies have used handicapped or disabled term synonymously but the findings of one category of disability and even different level of single disability couldn't be applicable due to category and level wise variation of problems and needs. Most of the studies employed selected purposive or random sampling and selected students with disabilities ranging from 10 to 18 year age group either from special schools or integrated schools. Not a single study found on the students with disability studying at higher education level. Researcher have used either standardized or developed their own tools. Other tools used were questionnaires and inventories. Besides this, personal data sheets, interview schedules, check lists, institutional records and attitude scales. Technical information regarding the tools is less available like medium of developed tools. Diagnostic tests, language development tests, assessment tests for different areas should be developed for maximizing educational opportunities of the students with disability.

- In most of researches, parametric statistics have been widely used. The data relating to children with disability neither fulfill the normality assumption nor random selection (Janigra and Mukhopadhyay, 1991) due to variance in their response based on their disabilities. The reported statistics leads the results much beyond than the desired.

The reported studies are indeed low in comparison with other areas of education, Jangira and Mukhopadhyay (1991) mentioned lack of interest among the universities and research institutions and lack of expertise as the major reasons for low yield of research in special education. From the emerged trend, it seemed clearly that Government's efforts for the education of children with disabilities and even PWD Act (1995) failed to increase interest among researchers in this area. Lack of availability of proper fund may be also affecting research in this field. Funding agencies should encourage researchers in this field through providing proper fund to doctoral or institutional studies.

On the basis of the above trend, the following **PRIORITY AREAS** demands immediate attention for undertaking research in special education :

Teaching-Learning

- More specific, precise and scientific researches are needed to make education of students with disability a reality in practice on a larger scale than present.
- Use of education in vocational as well as community life by the persons with disability should be studied.

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- Life of persons with disability after completion of the education/vocation could be studied.
- For measuring the effect of PWD Act-1995, survey could be conducted in institutes as well as in Government and private employment sectors which can bring the real picture of Government's efforts for mainstreaming the disabled.
- Classroom environment in integrated setting need to be studied.
- Reaction of teachers and students towards the students with disability also should be studied.

Management and Facilities

- Status of supporting systems, its delivery, rehabilitation services and help seeking behaviour should be thrust areas for the future research.
- Educational facilities for children with disability under the scheme of Integrated Education of Disabled Children. More studies on the facilities available, its usage and the needs of the children with disability needs urgent attention.
- Management of special education, co-ordinating structure at national and local levels and linking with schools have to be paid attention.
- Most of the researches conducted were addressing to single disability only. A research on multiple disabilities requires urgent attention as the country moves towards universal enrollment.

Use of Technology

- Researches have been conducted on the perceptions of and effectiveness of ET for other students but no any research addressing suitability of developed material or programme to the students with disability.
- Development and effectiveness of multi-media packages could be conducted. Developed packages needs to be tested in different modes. Software packages needs to develop for the different categories of disability which can do self-learning.
- Research on the application of the technology to meet special educational needs in the classroom and through distance mode is required.
- Effectiveness and extent of integration need to study for bringing actual picture regarding the integrated education and according to modifications can be done.
- Studies on students with disability in higher education have to be conducted.

Teacher Training

- Studies on special education and their teacher education can be conducted.
- Teacher and resource teacher of inclusive education needs attention.
- Present status of pre-service and in-service training provided to the teachers in the area of special education as government made integration of students with disability in general schools.
- More teacher training programmes/modules needs to develop for training pre-service as well as in-service teachers.

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